

On Solvability of Stochastic Differential Inclusions with Current Velocities. II

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Abstract

An existence of solution theorem is obtained for stochastic differential inclusions given in terms of the so-called current velocities (direct analogs of ordinary velocity of deterministic systems) and quadratic mean derivatives (giving information on the diffusion coefficient) on the flat n -dimensional torus. The set-valued current velocity part has a smooth selector and the set-valued quadratic part takes values in symmetric $(2, 0)$ tensor fields with given (constant) determinant. The values of current velocity parts are closed and bounded. The right-hand side of quadratic part is upper semi-continuous, its values are closed, bounded and satisfy some additional hypotheses that replace the convexity condition.

Key words: Mean derivatives; stochastic differential inclusions; group $SL(n)$

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Introduction

In [2] an existence theorem for differential inclusions with current velocities having single-valued part for quadratic mean derivative, was obtained under some very strong conditions. Then in [8] in some sense the opposite problem was considered, i.e., the current velocity part was single-valued and smooth while the quadratic part was set-valued and took values in the symmetric $(2, 0)$ -tensors with unit determinant.

In this paper we deal with the case where both current velocity and quadratic parts are set-valued. We assume that the current velocity part has a smooth selector (some conditions, under which this happens, are obtained, say, in [1, 4]). For the set-valued quadratic right-hand side we assume that it takes values in the symmetric $(2, 0)$ -tensors with constant (equal to some $C > 0$) determinant. The values of current velocity parts are closed and bounded. The right-hand side of quadratic part is upper semi-continuous and its values are closed, bounded and satisfy some additional hypotheses that replace the convexity condition.

To avoid some technical difficulties we consider the inclusions on a flat n -dimensional torus \mathcal{T}^n . This means that the torus is considered as a quotient space of \mathbb{R}^n relative to the integral lattice and that the Riemannian metric on \mathcal{T}^n is inherited from the Euclidean metric in \mathbb{R}^n . Everywhere below we use the operations of addition and subtraction of points and integration in \mathcal{T}^n as in \mathbb{R}^n modulo factorization relative to the integral lattice. The construction and notation of stochastic integrals and stochastic differential equations on \mathcal{T}^n are the same as in \mathbb{R}^n because of the use of Euclidean metric.

The detailed exposition of preliminary notions and facts used in the paper, can be found in [7].

For convenience, here we repeat some basic definitions and constructions from [8].

Everywhere in the paper we use Einstein's convention of summation relative to a shared upper and lower index (see, e.g., [7]).

1 Preliminaries on mean derivatives

Consider the n -dimensional flat torus \mathcal{T}^n . We shall deal with stochastic processes in \mathcal{T}^n given on a certain probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, $t \in [0, T] \subset \mathbb{R}$.

Denote by \mathcal{P}_t^ξ the sub- σ -algebra of \mathcal{F} generated by preimages of Borel sets from $\mathfrak{h} \mathcal{T}^n$ by all mappings $\xi(s) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ for $0 \leq s \leq t$; \mathcal{P}_t^ξ is called the "past" for $\xi(t)$.

Denote by \mathcal{N}_t^ξ the sub- σ -algebra of \mathcal{F} generated by preimages of Borel sets from \mathcal{T}^n by the mapping $\xi(t) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{T}^n$; \mathcal{N}_t^ξ is called the "present" for $\xi(t)$.

The sub- σ -algebras \mathcal{P}_t^ξ and \mathcal{N}_t^ξ for all t are supposed to be complete, i.e., containing all sets of probability zero. Obviously \mathcal{N}_t^ξ is a sub- σ -algebra in \mathcal{P}_t^ξ .

For the sake of convenience we denote by E_t^ξ the conditional expectation $E(\cdot | \mathcal{N}_t^\xi)$ with respect to \mathcal{N}_t^ξ for $\xi(t)$.

As in [9, 10, 11], we introduce the following notions of forward and backward mean derivatives.

Definition 1.1. (i) *The forward mean derivative $D\xi(t)$ of $\xi(t)$ at the time*

instant t is an L_1 random element of the form

$$D\xi(t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow +0} E_t^\xi \left(\frac{\xi(t + \Delta t) - \xi(t)}{\Delta t} \right), \quad (1.1)$$

where the limit is supposed to exist in $L_1(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbf{P})$ and $\Delta t \rightarrow +0$ means that Δt tends to 0 and $\Delta t > 0$.

(ii) The backward mean derivative $D_*\xi(t)$ of $\xi(t)$ at t is the L_1 -random element

$$D_*\xi(t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow +0} E_t^\xi \left(\frac{\xi(t) - \xi(t - \Delta t)}{\Delta t} \right) \quad (1.2)$$

where (as well as in (i)) the limit is assumed to exist in $L^1(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbf{P})$ and $\Delta t \rightarrow +0$ means that $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta t > 0$.

As usual in the machinery of conditional expectation (see, e.g., [12]), there exist Borel measurable vector fields $a^\xi(t, m)$ and $a_*^\xi(t, m)$ such that $D\xi(t) = a^\xi(t, \xi(t))$ and $D_*\xi(t) = a_*^\xi(t, \xi(t))$, respectively (see [9, 10, 11]).

Definition 1.2. The derivative $D_S = \frac{1}{2}(D + D_*)$ is called the symmetric mean derivative. The derivative $D_A = \frac{1}{2}(D - D_*)$ is called the antisymmetric mean derivative.

Consider the vectors

$$v^\xi(t, x) = \frac{1}{2}(a^\xi(t, x) + a_*^\xi(t, x))$$

and

$$u^\xi(t, x) = \frac{1}{2}(a^\xi(t, x) - a_*^\xi(t, x)).$$

Definition 1.3. $v^\xi(t) = v^\xi(t, \xi(t)) = D_S\xi(t)$ is called the current velocity of the process $\xi(t)$; $u^\xi(t) = u^\xi(t, \xi(t)) = D_A\xi(t)$ is called the osmotic velocity of the process $\xi(t)$.

The physical meaning of current velocity is a direct analog of the ordinary velocity of a deterministic process. The osmotic velocity measures how fast the randomness increases. This interpretation becomes clear from the following features of v^ξ and u^ξ (see [11]).

Consider an autonomous smooth field of non-degenerate linear operators $A(x) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, $x \in \mathcal{T}^n$. Suppose that $\xi(t)$ is a diffusion type process whose diffusion integrand is $A(\xi(t))$. Then its diffusion coefficient $A(x)A^*(x)$ is a smooth field of symmetric positive definite $(2, 0)$ -tensors with matrices $\alpha(x) = (\alpha^{ij}(x))$. Since all those matrices are non-degenerate, the field of inverse matrices (α_{ij}) exists and is smooth and at any x the matrix $(\alpha_{ij})(x)$ is symmetric and positive definite. Thus it defines a new Riemannian metric (symmetric positive

definite $(0, 2)$ -tensor field) $\alpha(\cdot, \cdot) = \alpha_{ij} dx^i dx^j$ on \mathbb{R}^n . Consider the Riemannian volume form of this Riemannian metric $\Lambda_\alpha = \sqrt{\det(\alpha_{ij})} dx^1 \wedge dx^2 \wedge \cdots \wedge dx^n$.

Denote by $\rho^\xi(t, x)$ the probability density of $\xi(t)$ with respect to the volume form $dt \wedge \Lambda_\alpha = \sqrt{\det(\alpha_{ij})} dt \wedge dx^1 \wedge dx^2 \wedge \cdots \wedge dx^n$ on $[0, T] \times \mathcal{T}^n$, i.e., for any continuous bounded function $f : [0, T] \times \mathcal{T}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the relation

$$\int_0^T E(f(t, \xi(t))) dt = \int_0^T \left(\int_{\Omega} f(t, \xi(t)) d\mathbf{P} \right) dt = \int_{[0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^n} f(t, x) \rho^\xi(t, x) dt \wedge \Lambda_\alpha \quad (1.3)$$

holds. Then

$$u^\xi(t, x) = \frac{1}{2} \text{Grad} \log \rho^\xi(t, x) = \text{Grad} \log \sqrt{\rho^\xi(t, x)}, \quad (1.4)$$

where *Grad* denotes the gradient with respect to the Riemannian metric $\alpha(\cdot, \cdot)$.

For $v^\xi(t, x)$ and $\rho^\xi(t, x)$ the so called equation of continuity

$$\frac{\partial \rho^\xi(t, x)}{\partial t} = -\text{Div}(v^\xi(t, x) \rho^\xi(t, x)) \quad (1.5)$$

holds, where *Div* denotes divergence with respect to the Riemannian metric $\alpha(\cdot, \cdot)$.

Following [2] we introduce the differential operator D_2 that differentiates an L_1 random process $\xi(t)$, $t \in [0, T]$ according to the rule

$$D_2 \xi(t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow +0} E_t^\xi \left(\frac{(\xi(t + \Delta t) - \xi(t))(\xi(t + \Delta t) - \xi(t))^*}{\Delta t} \right), \quad (1.6)$$

where $(\xi(t + \Delta t) - \xi(t))$ is considered as a column vector (vector in \mathbb{R}^n), $(\xi(t + \Delta t) - \xi(t))^*$ is a row vector (transposed, or conjugate vector) and the limit is supposed to exist in $L_1(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbf{P})$. We emphasize that the matrix product of a column on the left and a row on the right is a matrix with rank 1 but after passing to limit and taking conditional expectation $D_2 \xi(t)$ becomes a symmetric semi-positive definite matrix function on $[0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^n$ (in many cases positive definite). We call D_2 the quadratic mean derivative. It takes values in the set $(2, 0)$ -tensors having symmetric positive semi-definite matrices.

As mentioned above, the notion of current velocity is analogous to ordinary velocity for a non-random process. Thus, from the physical point of view, it is an important problem to study equations and inclusions with current velocities.

Let $v(t, m)$ be a vector field and $\alpha(t, m)$ be a symmetric positive semi-definite $(2, 0)$ -tensor field on \mathcal{T}^n . The system

$$\begin{cases} D_S \xi(t) &= v(t, \xi(t)) \\ D_2 \xi(t) &= \alpha(t, \xi(t)) \end{cases} \quad (1.7)$$

is called *the first order differential equation with current velocities*.

Note that equation (1.7) on the flat torus \mathcal{T}^n can be considered as an equation on \mathbb{R}^n periodic in space variables.

Definition 1.4. We say that (1.7) on \mathcal{T}^n has a solution on $[0, T]$ with initial condition $\xi(0) = \xi_0$ if there exists a probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ and a process $\xi(t)$ given on $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ and taking values in \mathcal{T}^n such that $\xi(0) = \xi_0$ and for almost all $t \in [0, T]$ equation (1.7) is satisfied \mathbb{P} -a.s. by $\xi(t)$.

Theorem 1.1. Let $v : [0, T] \times \mathcal{T}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ be smooth and $\alpha : \mathcal{T}^n \rightarrow S_+(n)$ be smooth and autonomous (so it determines the Riemannian metric $\alpha(\cdot, \cdot)$ on \mathcal{T}^n , introduced above). Let ξ_0 be a random element with values in \mathcal{T}^n whose probability density ρ_0 with respect to the volume form Λ_α of $\alpha(\cdot, \cdot)$ on \mathcal{T}^n (see above) is smooth and nowhere equal to zero. Then for the initial condition $\xi(0) = \xi_0$ equation (1.7) has a solution that is well-defined on the entire interval $t \in [0, T]$.

Theorem 1.1 is a simple corollary to [2, Theorem 4.1] (see also [7, Theorem 8.50]). Here we use the fact that on the compact manifold \mathcal{T}^n the right-hand sides of (1.7) are uniformly bounded and so the hypothesis of [2, Theorem 4.1] is fulfilled.

Introduce $p_0 = \log \rho_0$ and consider $p(t, m) = \log \rho^\xi(t, m)$ where $\rho^\xi(t, m)$ is the density (1.3) corresponding to the solution $\xi(t)$ of (1.7). It is shown in the proof of [2, Theorem 4.1] (see also [7, Theorem 8.50]) that $p(t, m)$ is well-posed and takes the form

$$p(t, m) = p_0(g_{-t}(m)) - \int_0^t (\text{Div } v)(s, g_s(g_{-t}(m))) ds \quad (1.8)$$

where Div is the divergence with respect to $\alpha(\cdot, \cdot)$ and g_t is the flow of smooth vector field $v(t, m)$.

2 Some technical constructions

Everywhere below we denote by $S_+(n)$ the set of symmetric positive definite $n \times n$ matrices.

In [2], on the basis of Hauss decomposition (see [14]), every matrix $\alpha \in S_+(n)$ is represented in the form $\alpha = \zeta \delta \zeta^*$ where ζ is a lower-triangle matrix with units on the diagonal, ζ^* is its transposed matrix, i.e., an upper-triangle matrix with units on the diagonal, and δ is a diagonal matrix whose angular minors (note that they all are positive) coincide with those of α . Denote the diagonal elements of δ by $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_n$. Then the matrix $A = \zeta \sqrt{\delta}$ where $\sqrt{\delta}$ is the diagonal matrix with $\sqrt{\delta_1}, \dots, \sqrt{\delta_n}$ on the diagonal, is such that $\alpha = AA^*$. If we deal with a continuous (smooth, measurable) field $\alpha(t, m)$, $t \in \mathbb{R}$ and $m \in \mathcal{T}^n$, of the above matrices, the corresponding matrices $A(t, m)$ are also continuous (smooth, measurable, respectively).

Denote by $T_-(n)$ the set of lower-triangle $n \times n$ matrices with zeros on the diagonal that is obviously a linear subspace in \mathbb{R}^{n^2} , the linear space of all

$n \times n$ matrices. It is evident that the matrix ζ introduced above, belongs to the linear submanifold $\mathbb{T}_-(n) + I$ in \mathbb{R}^{n^2} where I is the unit $n \times n$ matrix. Denote by $\mathbb{T} : S_+(n) \rightarrow \mathbb{T}_-(n)$ the smooth mapping that sends $\alpha \in S_+(n)$ to

$$\mathbb{T}\alpha = \zeta - I \in \mathbb{T}_-(n). \quad (2.1)$$

Now specify some $C > 0$ and denote by S_{LC} the set of matrices from $S_+(n)$ having determinants equal to C . In particular, this means that $\delta_1 \cdot \dots \cdot \delta_n = C$ and $\sqrt{\delta_1} \cdot \dots \cdot \sqrt{\delta_n} = \sqrt{C}$ where the dot denotes multiplication.

Denote by $\mathbb{L}_0(n)$ the linear subspace in \mathbb{R}^n consisting of vectors $X = (X^1, \dots, X^n)$ such that $X^1 + \dots + X^n = 0$.

Introduce the smooth mapping $\mathbb{L}_C : S_{LC} \rightarrow \mathbb{L}_0$, that sends a symmetric matrix $\alpha \in S_{LC}$ to

$$\mathbb{L}_C(\alpha) = \left(\log \frac{\sqrt{\delta_1}}{\sqrt{C}}, \dots, \log \frac{\sqrt{\delta_n}}{\sqrt{C}} \right) \in \mathbb{L}_0(n). \quad (2.2)$$

Note that $\mathbb{T}_-(n)$ and $\mathbb{L}_0(n)$ are linear spaces and so the notion of convex set is well-posed in them.

Lemma 2.1. *For every smooth autonomous $(2,0)$ -tensor field $\alpha(m)$ on flat torus \mathcal{T}^n with values in S_{LC} :*

(i) *The volume form Λ_α of the corresponding Riemannian metric $\alpha(\cdot, \cdot)$ (see above) equals $\sqrt{C}\Lambda_E$ where Λ_E is the volume form of the Euclidean metric on \mathcal{T}^n inherited from \mathbb{R}^n after factorization with respect to the integral lattice.*

(ii) *For every smooth vector field $v(t, m)$ on \mathcal{T}^n its divergence $\text{Div } v$ with respect to Λ_α coincides with ordinary divergence $\text{div } v$ (i.e., with respect to Λ_E).*

(iii) *For every random element having values in \mathcal{T}^n , its distribution with respect to Λ_α equals the distribution with respect to Λ_E divided by \sqrt{C} .*

Proof. Indeed, $\Lambda_\alpha = \sqrt{\det(\alpha_{ij})} dq^1 \wedge \dots \wedge dq^n$ and since $\det(\alpha_{ij}) = C$, we obtain that it equals $\sqrt{C}\Lambda_E = C dq^1 \wedge \dots \wedge dq^n$.

Recall that the divergence $\text{Div } v$ is found from the equality

$$\mathcal{L}_v \Lambda_\alpha = (\text{Div } v) \Lambda_\alpha$$

where \mathcal{L}_v is the Lie derivative by v (see details, e.g., in [7]). Recall also that $\mathcal{L}_v \Lambda_\alpha = d(v \lrcorner \Lambda_\alpha)$ where \lrcorner denotes the internal multiplication of vectors and differential forms. Since C is constant, $d(v \lrcorner \Lambda_\alpha) = \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial q^i} \sqrt{C} \Lambda_E = \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial q^i} \Lambda_\alpha$. Hence $\text{Div } v = \frac{\partial v^i}{\partial q^i} = \text{div } v$.

Assertion (iii) follows from (i). □

3 The main result

Let $\mathbf{v}(t, m)$ be a set-valued vector field and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t, m)$ a set-valued symmetric positive semi-definite $(2, 0)$ -tensor field on \mathcal{T}^n . The system of the form

$$\begin{cases} D_S \xi(t) \in \mathbf{v}(t, \xi(t)), \\ D_2 \xi(t) \in \boldsymbol{\alpha}(t, \xi(t)). \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

is called a first order differential inclusion with current velocities. The notion of solution of (3.1) is quite analogous to that from Definition 1.4.

Below we suppose that the set-valued field $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ satisfies the following condition:

Condition 3.1. (i) *The set-valued $(2, 0)$ -tensor field $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ on \mathcal{T}^n takes values in S_{LC} ; it is autonomous and upper semicontinuous.*

(ii) *The values of $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ are closed and uniformly bounded.*

(iii) *For every $m \in \mathcal{T}^n$ the set $\mathbb{T}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}(m))$ (see (2.1)) is convex in $\mathbb{T}_-(n)$ and the set $\mathbb{L}_C(\boldsymbol{\alpha}(m))$ (see (2.2)) is convex in $\mathbb{L}_0(n)$.*

For $\mathbf{v}(t, m)$ we suppose that it has a smooth single-valued selector denoted by $v(t, m)$. Recall that some conditions, under which a set-valued mapping has a smooth selector, are obtained in [1, 4].

Theorem 3.1. *Let $\mathbf{v}(t, m)$ be a set-valued vector field on \mathcal{T}^n having smooth single-valued selector $v(t, m)$ for $t \in [0, T]$. Let also $\boldsymbol{\alpha}(m)$ be a set-valued $(2, 0)$ -tensor field that satisfies Condition 3.1. Consider a random ξ_0 element with values in \mathcal{T}^n whose probability density with respect to the volume form Λ_E equals $\sqrt{C}\rho_0$ where ρ_0 is smooth and nowhere equal to zero. Then for the initial condition $\xi(0) = \xi_0$ inclusion (3.1) has a solution that is well-defined on the entire interval $t \in [0, T]$.*

Proof. Specify a sequence of positive numbers $\varepsilon_k \rightarrow 0$. Since the mappings \mathbb{T} and \mathbb{L}_C are smooth, the set-valued mappings $\mathbb{T}\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ with values in $\mathbb{T}_-(n)$ and $\mathbb{L}_C\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ with values in $\mathbb{L}_0(n)$ are upper semicontinuous since such is $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$. By Condition 3.1 their values are convex, closed and uniformly bounded. Then by [3, Theorem 2] (see also [7, Theorem 4.11]) there exist the sequences of single-valued continuous ε_k -approximations that point-wise converge to Borel measurable selectors of $\mathbb{T}\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ and $\mathbb{L}_C\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, respectively. Without loss of generality those approximations can be supposed as smooth. Thus there exists a sequence α_k of single-valued smooth uniformly bounded $(2, 0)$ -tensor fields with values in S_{LC} that point-wise converges to a Borel measurable selector $\alpha(m)$ of $\boldsymbol{\alpha}(m)$. The components of $\alpha_k(m)$ will be denoted as α_k^{ij} .

Construct the Riemannian metrics $\alpha_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ from tensor fields $\alpha_k(m)$.
 Consider the sequence of equations

$$\begin{cases} D_S \xi(t) &= v(t, \xi(t)) \\ D_2 \xi(t) &= \alpha_k(t, \xi(t)) \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

Note that by Lemma 2.1 for those equations we can consider the same initial value ξ_0 since its densities with respect to all $\alpha_k(\cdot, \cdot)$ coincide with ρ_0 . All equations (3.2) satisfy the conditions of Theorem 1.1, so there exist solutions $\xi_k(t)$ of those equations.

From Lemma 2.1 it follows that the functions $p(t, m)$ defined by (1.8) for all $\xi_k(t)$ coincide (in particular this means that the densities $\rho(t, m)$ coincide as well).

For a solution $\xi_k(t)$ the osmotic velocity takes the form

$$u_k(t, m) = \frac{1}{2} \text{Grad}_k p(t, m)$$

where Grad_k is the gradient calculated with respect to $\alpha_k(\cdot, \cdot)$. One can easily show by the definition of gradient that the coordinate presentation of $\text{Grad}_k p(t, m)$ has the form $(\text{Grad}_k p(t, m))^i = \alpha_k^{ij} \frac{\partial p}{\partial q^j}$. Thus, from the hypothesis and from Condition 3.1 it follows that all $u_k(t, m)$ are smooth and uniformly bounded. Since the components α_k^{ij} point-wise converge to the components α^{ij} of $\alpha(m)$, the vectors $u_k(t, m)$ point-wise converge to $u(t, m)$ with components $u^i = \frac{1}{2} \alpha^{ij} \frac{\partial p}{\partial q^j}$.

Introduce the vector fields $a_k(t, m) = v(t, m) + u_k(t, m)$, denote its point-wise limit by $a(t, m)$. As it is mentioned in Section , every $\alpha_k(m)$ can be represented as $\alpha_k(m) = A_k(m)A_k^*(m)$. By construction the sequence $A_k(m)$ point-wise converge to the Borel-measurable field $A(m)$ such that $\alpha(m) = A(m)A^*(m)$.

Consider the sequence of Itô type stochastic differential equations

$$\xi_k(t) = \xi_0 + \int_0^t a_k(s, \xi(s)) ds + \int_0^t A_k(s, \xi(s)) dw(s) \quad (3.3)$$

on \mathcal{T}^n . Since the coefficients of (3.3) for all k are smooth and bounded, all the equations have unique strong solutions well-defined on the entire interval $[0, T]$. On the Banach manifold $C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)$ of continuous curves in \mathcal{T}^n introduce the σ -algebra \mathcal{C} generated by cylinder sets and denote by μ_k the measure on $(C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n), \mathcal{C})$ generated by the solution $\xi_k(t)$ of (3.3). Introduce also the family of complete sub- σ -algebras \mathcal{P}_t generated by cylinder sets with bases in $[0, t]$, $t \in [0, T]$.

Since equations (3.3) can be considered as the ones in \mathbb{R}^n with space-periodic coefficients, one can apply [6, Corollary III.2] and show that the set $\{\mu_k\}$ of measures on $(C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n), \mathcal{C})$ is weakly compact. Hence we can select a sub-sequence that weakly converges to a certain measure μ . Without loss of generality we can suppose that the sequence μ_k weakly converges to μ . Consider the coordinate process $\xi(t)$ on the probability space $(C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n), \mathcal{C}, \mu)$, i.e., for every elementary event $x(\cdot) \in C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)$, by definition $\xi(t, x(\cdot)) = x(t)$. Note that \mathcal{P}_t is the “past” for $\xi(t)$. As usual, \mathcal{N}_t^ξ is a sub- σ -algebra of \mathcal{P}_t .

By construction, $D_S \xi_k(t) = v(t, \xi_k(t))$ for all k . This means that for every bounded continuous real-valued function f on $C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)$ measurable with respect to \mathcal{N}_t^ξ , the equality

$$\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} [x(t + \Delta t) - x(t - \Delta t) - v(t, x(t))] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu_k = 0$$

holds for all k .

Specify an arbitrary $\varepsilon > 0$. Since μ_k weakly converges to μ , there exists $K(\varepsilon)$ such that for all $k > K(\varepsilon)$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} [x(t + \Delta t) - x(t - \Delta t) - v(t, x(t))] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu_k \right. \\ & \left. - \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} [x(t + \Delta t) - x(t - \Delta t) - v(t, x(t))] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu \right\| < \varepsilon. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\left\| \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} [x(t + \Delta t) - x(t - \Delta t) - v(t, x(t))] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu \right\| < \varepsilon.$$

Since ε is an arbitrary positive number and f is an arbitrary function, measurable with respect to \mathcal{N}_t^ξ , this means that

$$D_S \xi(t) = v(t, \xi(t)). \quad (3.4)$$

By construction, for every $\xi_k(t)$ its quadratic derivative equals $\alpha_k(\xi_k(t))$. This means that for each $f(x(\cdot))$ as above we obtain the equality

$$\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} [(x(t + \Delta t) - x(t))(x(t + \Delta t) - x(t))^* - \alpha_k(x(t))] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu_k = 0.$$

Since $\alpha_k(t, m)$ tends to $\alpha(t, m)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ point-wise, it tends a.s. with respect to all μ_k and with respect to μ . Specify $\delta > 0$. By Egorov’s theorem (see, e.g., [13]) for any i there exists a subset $\tilde{K}_\delta^i \subset C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)$ such that $(\mu_i)(\tilde{K}_\delta^i) > 1 - \delta$, and the sequence $\alpha_k(x(t))$ converges to $\alpha(x(t))$ uniformly

on \tilde{K}_δ^i . Introduce $\tilde{K}_\delta = \bigcup_{i=0}^{\infty} \tilde{K}_\delta^i$. The sequence $\alpha_k(x(t))$ converges to $\alpha(x(t))$ uniformly on \tilde{K}_δ and $\mu_i(\tilde{K}_\delta) > 1 - \delta$ for all i and $\mu(\tilde{K}_\delta) > 1 - \delta$.

Note that $\alpha(x(t))$ is continuous on a set of full measure μ on $C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)$. Indeed, consider a sequence $\delta_i \rightarrow 0$ and the corresponding sequence \tilde{K}_{δ_i} . By the above construction $\alpha(x(t))$ is a uniform limit of continuous functions on each \tilde{K}_{δ_i} . Thus it is continuous on each \tilde{K}_{δ_i} and so, on every finite union $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \tilde{K}_{\delta_i}$. Evidently $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(\bigcup_{i=1}^n \tilde{K}_{\delta_i}) = 1$.

Because of the above uniform convergence on \tilde{K}_δ for all k and boundedness of $f(x(\cdot))$ we get that for k large enough

$$\left\| \int_{\tilde{K}_\delta} [\alpha_k(x(t)) - \alpha(x(t))] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu_k \right\| < \delta.$$

Since $f(x(\cdot))$ is bounded, there is some $\Xi > 0$ such that $|f(x(\cdot))| < \Xi$ for all $x(\cdot)$. Recall that all $\alpha_k(m)$ and $\alpha(m)$ are uniformly bounded, i.e., their norms are not greater than a certain $Q > 0$. Then, since $\mu_k(C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n) \setminus \tilde{K}_\delta) < \delta$ for all k large enough, we obtain that

$$\left\| \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n) \setminus \tilde{K}_\delta} [\alpha_k(x(t)) - \alpha(x(t))] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu_k \right\| < 2\delta Q \Xi$$

for all k large enough. Since δ is an arbitrary positive number, we obtain that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} [\alpha_k(x(t)) - \alpha(x(t))] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu_k = 0.$$

The function $\alpha(x(t))$ is μ -a.s. continuous and bounded on $C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)$ (see above). Since in addition the measures μ_k weakly converge to μ , by Lemma from [5, Section VI.1] we obtain that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} \alpha(x(t)) f(x(\cdot)) d\mu_k = \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} \alpha(x(t)) f(x(\cdot)) d\mu.$$

Obviously

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} [(x(t + \Delta t) - x(t))(x(t + \Delta t) - x(t))^*] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu_k \\ &= \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} [(x(t + \Delta t) - x(t))(x(t + \Delta t) - x(t))^*] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \int_{C^0([0, T], \mathcal{T}^n)} [(x(t + \Delta t) - x(t))(x(t + \Delta t) - x(t))^* - \alpha(x(t))] f(x(\cdot)) d\mu = 0.$$

Since $f(x(\cdot))$ is an arbitrary bounded continuous function, measurable with respect to \mathcal{N}_t^ξ , this means that $D_2\xi(t) = \alpha(\xi(t))$. But by construction $\alpha(\xi(t)) \in \alpha(\xi(t))$ μ -a.s.

Together with (3.4) this means that $\xi(t)$ is a solution of inclusion (3.1) we are looking for. \square

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